

Automated 3D tree-ring detection and ring-width calculation from X-ray computed tomography

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Tree ring analysis is essential in the understanding, modelling and assessment of the evolution of wood samples over time. It provides quantitative data about the whole ring structure which can be used, for example, to measure the impact of the fluctuating environment on the tree growth, to support global vegetation models and for the dendrochronological analysis of archaeological wooden artefacts. There currently exist several methods for tree-ring detection and tree-ring parameters estimation from imaging data. However, despite advances in computer vision and edge recognition algorithms, detection of tree-rings is mostly limited to 2D datasets

and performed in some cases manually. This contribution presents a new approach to extract the whole 3D tree-ring structure directly from X-ray computed tomography data and illustrates how average tree-ring widths can be estimated from it. The approach relies on a modified Canny edge detection algorithm, which detect fully connected tree-ring edges throughout the measured image stack. The obtained results show that the approach performs well on six tree species having conifer, ring-porous and diffuse-porous ring boundary structure. In our study image denoising proved to be a critical step to achieve accurate results.